

CHARACTERISTICS OF PHOSPHORUS DECOMPOSITION AND ORGANIC ACID SYNTHESIS OF DAIRY FERMENTING BACTERIA

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Abstract. *Lactobacillus plantarum M1, Pediococcus pentosaceus A1 and Enterococcus faesium A2 strains of lactobacilli, selected in order to increase the productivity of agricultural crops, have been found to have an active phosphorus decomposition property. It was found that the property of phosphorus decomposition is carried out depending on the synthesis of organic acids in microorganisms. This increases soil fertility and ensures healthy development of plants.*

Keywords: *milk-fermenting bacteria, phosphorus decomposition, lactobacilli, organic acid, succinic acid, acetic acid, 3-phenyllactic acid.*

INTRODUCTION

Currently, chemical fertilizers and pesticides are widely used in agriculture to increase productivity. However, the constant use of these fertilizers leads to a decrease in soil fertility, the destruction of microflora, and a decrease in productivity. This has a negative impact on human health and the general ecological situation. The interaction of plants and microbes helps to increase soil fertility in agriculture, reduce plant diseases and protect them from adverse environmental conditions [1]. Lactobacilli are a group of non-spore-forming, gram-positive cocci or bacillus bacteria capable of converting carbohydrate substrates into organic acids and producing various metabolites. Lactose-fermenting bacteria synthesize various biologically active substances: organic acids, vitamins, enzymes [2]. Soil microorganisms ensure the assimilation of nutrients by plants [3]. On average, the amount of phosphorus in the soil is about 0.5%, but only 0.1% of this phosphorus is used by plants [4]. Mineral fertilizers are mainly used to eliminate phosphorus deficiency in the soil. Phosphorus that is not dissolved in the soil accumulates in a crystalline state, causing a decrease in soil fertility. This causes environmental problems [5]. Lactobacillus synthesizes a number of useful metabolites for the soil, their metabolites accelerate the growth of shoots and roots of plants and protect against various phytopathogenic fungi. It enriches the organic content of the soil by microorganisms and ensures the production of organic acid and bacteriocin metabolites [6]. Phosphate-soluble bacteria dissolve undissolved phosphorus in the soil and make it absorbable by plants [7]. In addition to the ability to solubilize phosphate and potassium, lactobacilli also have the ability to produce siderophores [8]. The use of phosphate-solubilizing bacteria is considered as a new area of plant productivity improvement. As a result of research, it was confirmed that the process of dissolving phosphorus by microorganisms is related to the process of organic acid production. Under the influence of organic acids synthesized by microorganisms, insoluble phosphorus minerals are decomposed. Soil in an alkaline state precipitates mineral substances, which accumulate and lead to a decrease in soil efficiency [9].

Lactobacilli produce antifungal substances such as cyclic dipeptides, proteinaceous compounds, organic acids, fatty acids, 3-phenyllactic and reuterin [10]. Since recent years, studies have been carried out in Uzbekistan to determine the antifungal activity of lactobacilli isolated from various plant samples against phytopathogenic micromycetes harmful to agriculture. [11] Milk-fermenting bacteria Lactobacilli have been used in agriculture since recent years to protect plants from diseases and ensure growth, and various species have been identified in plant phyllosphere, seed endosphere and rhizosphere[12]. Crowley and colleagues reported that *Pediococcus pentosaceus* showed broad-spectrum antifungal activity against fungal pathogens of fruit crops [13]. In addition, lactobacilli synthesize 3-phenyllactic acid, which belongs to the phenolic group. 3-Phenyllactic acid (PLA) is a broad-spectrum antimicrobial compound active against phytopathogenic bacteria and fungi. There are two isomers of PLA that show antimicrobial activity, L-PLA and D-PLA. It shows more antimicrobial activity than D-PLA and L-PLA, and therefore it is of great interest as an antibiotic that controls bacteria and improves the quality of feed additives. Regulation of the metabolic pathway of PLA synthesis in lactic acid bacteria and its high production are also discussed[14]. Synthesis of 3-phenyllactic acid in lactic acid bacteria occurs as a result of amino acid metabolism, and the acids involved in the synthesis of PLA are phenylalanine and p-ketoglutarate. Phenylalanine is first transaminated to phenylpyruvic acid, and phenylpyruvic is then converted to 3-phenyllactic[15]. Antifungal activity of lactobacilli is due to acidic compounds such as 3-phenyllactic acid or organic acids rather than proteins or peptides molecules[16]. In addition, researchers are studying the synthesis of plant-growing phytohormones (gibberellin, indole acetic acid, auxin) by milk-fermenting bacteria [17].

MATERIALS AND METHODS.

Lactobacillus plantarum M1, *Pediococcus pentosaceus* A1 and *Enterococcus faecium* A2 strains, which have probiotic properties and are active against phytopathogenic microorganisms, were selected as objects of research. Pikovskaya's nutrient medium was prepared to determine the phosphorous decomposition properties of lactobacilli. Composition of Pikovskaya nutrient medium (g/l):

Yeast extract - 0.5, Glucose -10, $\text{Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$ -5, $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ - 0.5, NaCl - 0.2, KCl- 0.2, $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ - 0.1, $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ - 0.002, bromophenol blue - 0.025, Agar - 20 pH-7.0. We pour the prepared nutrient medium into Petri dishes and plant our milk-fermenting bacteria prepared by sowing on MRS agar with a hook into a petri dish. Quantitative analysis of acetic acid, lactic acid, propionic acid, and organic acids of lactobacilli strains was carried out. As a control, MRS-feed medium without lactobacilli strains was used. 50 μl reconstituted lactobacilli cultures were inoculated in 5 ml MRS-feed medium and incubated at 37°C for 18 h. The amount of organic acids of the studied samples was determined using the YuSSX (high-quality liquid chromatography) method. Agilent Technologies -1200 HPLC brand Agilent C18 column 5 μm , 4.6x250 mm. Separation of organic acids was carried out in isocratic elution mode, using 0.1% orthophosphoric acid and acetonitrile ratio (95:5) as the mobile phase. Detection was carried out at a wavelength of 210 nm, column temperature - 30°C, injection volume - 5 μl . Chemical reagents and purity > 99.9% (gradient level, for HPLC) obtained from Sigma-Aldrich were used. The number of standard samples of organic acids was dissolved in 1 ml of distilled water in special test tubes for analysis. Solutions were filtered using a 0.2 μm filter to remove mechanical and undissolved fine particles that could contaminate the chromatographic columns and cause a rapid decrease in efficiency, and then the sample solutions were introduced into a special compartment of the

designed chromatograph for the samples analyzed and the analysis was performed according to the developed method.

Centrifugation was performed at 8000 rpm for 10 min to remove proteins. The injection volume for each assay was 5 μ L. The results of the analysis were displayed on a computer monitor in the form of a chromatogram, and the software allowed automatic merging of the obtained peaks.

The obtained results: It was found that the lactobacilli strains isolated from the local plant samples from Uzbekistan are actively capable of decomposing phosphorus.

Table 1

Milk-fermenting bacteria	<i>L.plantarum</i> M1	<i>P. pentosaceus</i> A1	<i>E. faecium</i> A2
The diameter of the forming ring zones (mm)	30 mm	33 mm	38 mm

Lactobacillus L. plantarum M1 with a diameter of 30 mm, *P. pentosaceus* A1 with a diameter of 33 mm, and milk-fermenting bacteria *E. faecium* A2 with a diameter of 38 mm formed a ring zone, i.e., a yellow color in agar.

Figure 1. Phosphorus-degrading properties of milk-fermenting bacterial strains are shown by the agar stain method (Pikovskaya method).

Figure 2. Organic acid synthesis of lactobacilli

From the obtained results, it was known that among the tested strains, *P. pentosaceus* A-1 strain 43.28669 µg/ml, *E. faecium* A-2 strain 36.87946 µg/ml showed high acetic acid production properties. All strains were the leaders in the production of lactic acid, and the amount of lactic acid in its culture liquid was equal to 13.8 µg/ml on average. *P. pentosaceus* A-1 strain had a succinic acid content of 28.1 µg/ml.

L. plantarum M-1 synthesized 18.4 µg/ml and *E. faecium* 21.3 µg/ml of succinic acid. In addition, all studied strains synthesized oxalic acid. *L. plantarum* M-1 17.6 µg/ml, *P. pentosaceus* A-1 strain 16.5 µg/ml, and *E. faecium* A-2 strain 18 µg/ml were found to synthesize shavalic acid. Synthesis of organic acids in milk-fermenting bacteria determines antifungal activity against pathogenic bacteria and fungi.

In addition, the ability of the studied strains to synthesize 3-phenyllactic acid was determined in order to demonstrate the antagonism of bacteria against various conditionally pathogenic microbes and phytopathogenic fungi in an active state.

Table 1. Synthesis of 3-phenyllactic acid of the tested strains (mg/ml)

Strains being tested	<i>L.plantarum</i> M-1	<i>P.pentosaceus</i> A-1	<i>E.faecium</i> A-2
	Concentration mkg/ml		
PLA	1,92	2,38	2,64

The amount of 3-phenyllactic acid in lactobacilli strains was found to be synthesized by *L. plantarum* M-1 2.64 µg/ml, *P. pentosaceus* A-1 strain 1.92 µg/ml and *E. faecium* A-2 strain 2.38 µg/ml. This acid is important for blocking the growth of pathogenic microorganisms.

CONCLUSION

The obtained results show that the selected strains of *L. plantarum* M1, *P. pentosaceus* A1 and *E. faecium* A2 are actively capable of breaking down phosphorus. It was found that this process is related to the synthesis of volatile organic acids and 3-phenyllactic acid belonging to the phenolic group in microorganisms. Therefore, the strains of milk-fermenting bacteria isolated from different plants with probiotic properties have the synthesis of various important unique metabolites, and in the future, in the field of agriculture, they can develop alternative biological preparations that accelerate the growth of plants, protect them and replace harmful chemical preparations.

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